

A Thematic Content Analysis of Spiritual Identity in The Weekend's *Hurry Up Tomorrow*

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I. Introduction

Music is known for showing character and, rather, the development of such character. Popular musicians often utilize personas to separate their personal lives from their public performances. A known example of this is Abel Tesfaye, more commonly known as The Weeknd. His career began in 2011 with the *House of Balloons* mixtape and further evolved from underground R&B into one of the most successful music icons in history. This paper is designed to focus on the second trilogy in his discography (After Hours), which includes *After Hours* (2020), where The Weeknd is being consumed by sins, *Dawn FM* (2022), where The Weeknd is trapped in purgatory, and *Hurry Up Tomorrow* (2025), where The Weeknd is transitioning into heaven. The uniqueness of this trilogy originates from the utilization of theological archetypes to signify the growth of a character. While other albums in the trilogy and in his overall discography revolve mainly around sins and wrongdoings, *Hurry Up Tomorrow* is more related to the construction of a true identity through self-reflection and growth. This is why the album was chosen, as this construction of identity is directly tied to religious language and references. Religious identity, in this context, is described as the implementation of theological language, archetypes, and references to personal faith. This built up to my eventual research question: To what extent does The Weeknd use religious language and lyrics to construct a spiritual identity in *Hurry Up Tomorrow*?

II. Literature Review

Foundational Studies:

To start off, before understanding and reviewing lyrics, we must understand why music is a tool to discuss religious identity. Claudio Campesato (2023) discusses the concept of vis (natural power) and argues that music has a corporeal effect that can generate intense emotions. This music in *Hurry Up Tomorrow* creates a listening or receptive state where the listener is ready to hear a message of growth. Nick Zangwill (2024) provides a “smorgasbord” of different models to help us understand this. Specifically, his “Honey model” suggests that music acts like honey in order to make a religious message easier to swallow (ex. confession). Additionally, his Organic Unity Model suggests that the music and religious message eventually become one. For The Weeknd, the “honey” of his production allows him to deliver a theologically heavy message in his lyrics. This is further supported by a YouTube analysis of the trilogy, where creator TennisThom decoded each message in all three albums. This video also serves as background knowledge for this paper as it explains the storyline of the albums.

Porosity:

To analyze religious identity in an artist, we need to address the contradiction between the artist’s “secular” lifestyle and their “sacred” language. Edward Foley (2020) provides the theological framework for this idea through his concept of porosity. Foley argues that in Western academia, researchers often separate liturgy from worldly or common expression. However, he asserts that the boundaries between these topics are naturally fluid. He suggests that religious terminology, like altars, preachers, or sin, does not lose its theological weight despite being referenced in relation to a secular term. Foley directly justifies the investigation of *Hurry Up Tomorrow* as a

spiritual text, although it has significant ties within a commercial industry. This blend is also supported by Dustin D. Wiebe (2021), who reviews trends in musicology to define musicking as a socially situated act where everyday life and spirituality intersect. Wiebe's research suggests that spirituality is often found in the ineffable aspects of popular music rather than formal religious institutions. This is specifically true in genres of Hip-Hop and R&B. Research from the Virginia Commonwealth University (2020) found that artists like Kanye West do this often, where they reference religion in a secular space. This study explains that for many artists, secularity is not an obstacle to religious identity, but rather essential. To put this into the context of The Weeknd would be to showcase that, for example, his references to drug usage are not just secular motifs or themes but rather a foundation for his persona to ascend from.

Narrative Building:

The Weeknd's choice to structure these albums through a trilogy is an example of a method of identity construction called world-building. Mattia Merlini (2021) argues that concept albums have evolved into artist-built immersive narratives in order to maintain thematic consistency. This is shown as The Weeknd frames his albums as "Inferno", "Purgatorio", and "Paradiso", which are theological archetypes that are used to signify progression or growth within oneself. This narrative structure is more than a choice, as it is a scientifically recognized way to engage the human psyche. Alberhasky and Durkee (2024) explain that "songs tell a story" through an arc that provides listeners with a sense of emotional resolution. On a larger scale, Neto et al. (2025) identified the "Man in a Hole" arc as one of the recurring sequences in tracking listing. In this model, a character starts in a dark place, falls further, and then eventually climbs toward redemption. This is directly shown in The Weeknd's *After Hours* Trilogy as the first album (*After*

Hours) represents the fall into the “hole”, the second (*Dawn FM*) represents the liminal state in that hole, and the third (*Hurry Up Tomorrow*) represents the climb toward redemption or light. By using these studies, this paper establishes that Tesfaye is not selecting religious themes but rather using a scientifically based narrative structure to communicate personal growth and resurrection of self.

Soundscapes:

While the narrative structure provides the map for spiritual identity, the “soundscape” of the album provides the evidence of growth. An essential question in this research is how a listener perceives a character's identity through audio features alone. Preniqi et al. (2023) conducted a study linking music preferences and audio features to moral values. They found that humans subconsciously link specific soundscapes to morality. Specifically, music that is perceived as bright or euphoric is associated with higher moral value, and music with darker tones is associated with lower moral value. This connects directly to the transition within the trilogy, as *After Hours* utilizes heavier synths to represent a hell-like space and *Dawn FM* uses a stuck radio aesthetic to represent purgatory. However, *Hurry Up Tomorrow* utilizes what Alberhasky and Durkee (2024) would describe as a “resolution arc”. The audio features themselves are blissful and heavenly instrumentals that act as a sign of transcendence. By using these studies, this paper establishes that the construction of a spiritual identity is not merely a lyrical choice but a sonic one as well, despite only lyrical elements being studied.

Semiotics:

Beyond sound and lyrics, the construction of identity also relies on semiotics, or the study of signs, symbols, and motifs. Yudhanto and Risdianto (2022) provide a framework for this by

analyzing how visual and verbal signs have denotations and connotations (literal and implied meanings). Their study of the band *They Fell From The Sky* demonstrated that specific symbols, such as light or skull, carry deep meanings of struggle and resurrection. For The Weeknd, an example of this would be the transition of him in his bloodied red suit to his heavenly robes, which act as a visual semiotic sign of transcendence. In this study, semiotics will be used to decode specific signs of atonement. Campesato (2023) introduces the theological concept of *penitence* or *compunction*, which is a state of inner sorrow and awareness of sin that opens one up to the divine. This framework justifies why Category 2 of the codebook is essential to the paper. When The Weeknd uses lyrics about “washing” or “begging”, he is using symbolic language to signal that his persona is undergoing a cleansing process.

Gap:

Despite the large amounts of research on the “natural power” of music (Campesato, 2023) and the “porosity” of sacred and secular language (Foley, 2020), there is a significant gap in current literature regarding the real-time construction of identity in contemporary R&B. While studies like the VCU Scholars Compass (2020) have analyzed testifying in hip-hop, few have applied a full systematic, thematic content analysis to a full trilogy that explicitly uses theological archetypes (Inferno, Purgatorio, Paradiso) to signify the death of a persona. Existing research often focuses on the presence of religious words rather than on how a narrative arc uses these words to create a new spiritual identity. Furthermore, the “Man in a Hole” arc has only been identified but not used as a way to evaluate the transition of a persona from sin to transcendence. This study aims to fill that gap by applying the frameworks of porosity and semiotics to *Hurry Up Tomorrow*, providing a unique look at how the Paradiso phase of a trilogy serves as a tool for

an artist to remake an identity through religious language.

III. Methodology

Design:

This study utilizes a qualitative thematic content analysis of the lyrics from *Hurry Up Tomorrow*.

This method was selected as it allows for a systematic interpretation of symbolic language and narrative progression.

Data Collection:

The data consists of lyrics from 19 of the 22 tracks on the album as the song “I Can’t F*cking Sing” is a skit, “Until We’re Skin & Bones” is an instrumental. Another song, “Sao Paulo”, was excluded for two main reasons. One being that it was a primary collaboration with a featured artist Anitta who has a very distinct culture and linguistic framework based in Brazilian Funk, which makes the song function as an outlier inside the album. Another reason behind this decision was that the song is based more rhythmically and does not contain many theological semiotics that can be analysed by the studies set categories. By removing this track, the study maintains thematic validity, focusing only on the personas direct spiritual confessions. Any songs with features from other artists were only coded for lyrics said by The Weeknd. All lyrics were sourced from [Genius.com](https://www.genius.com). Genius was chosen as it is publicly available and is backed by: popular opinion, community-driven editing, artist recognition, and auditory recognition.

Codebook:

This method utilizes a codebook that is backed by the frameworks of Foley (2020) and Zangwill

(2024). In order to ensure this study's replicability, each code is defined by specific criteria of what it includes and excludes. A large portion of this method is based on resolving the porosity of the data. This is needed as in music, sacred and secular often blend together (Foley 2020). To reduce this, another category was added that ensures the study does not count religious language as something that is being used secularly. A good example of this would be the lyric "I wash my fears with whisky tears" (Cry for Me). Although this lyric utilizes the word "wash", which could fit in category 2, it's negated by the usage of whisky, as it's a non-religious term. This ultimately makes the lyric a secular one.

Category 1: Liminality (Purgatory): This category identifies lyrics referencing a state of transition or being "stuck" between two worlds. This includes lyrics where secular and sacred overlap in a state of waiting, confusion, or ambiguity. References to things in a dream-like way are also considered for this category (ex. the end, hurry up, wake up, ghost/spirit).

Category 2: Atonement: This category includes any mention or reference to sacraments used to remove a sin (ex. things like fire, water, washing). This category also includes any reference or pleas to a religious figure or authority. (ex. altars, preachers, god). Finally, this category also includes references to moral failure, a price, or desire for forgiveness (begging, paying, regrets)

Category 3: Transcendence: This category represents a transition from a persona of sin (The Weeknd) to a new identity constructed from a spiritual sense. This includes references to light or divine presence, ascension and escaping a trap or loop, and finally direct references to angels,

god or divinity as a source of peace and tranquility (ex. Angels, light, shining, fly away, resurrecting, come to life)

Category 4: Secular grounding: This concept of porosity, backed by Foley (2020), serves as a control variable to evaluate how spiritual identity has actually been affected. This category includes references to drugs or alcohol as a coping or escape, references to the music industry or money, and any description of sexual or physical desire. (ex. fame, “business life pimping”, “you got me on my knees”, “you're my favorite drug”)

IV. Analysis Metrics

The main metric of analysis for this study involves the systematic categorization of lyrical units into four distinct thematic codes derived from both the concepts of porosity (Foley, 2020) and the “Man in a Hole” narrative arc (Neto et al., 2025). In order to mitigate subjectivity from the researcher, each lyric was evaluated in two parts: First, the lyric was checked for the presence of theological semiotics, such as “fire”, “spirit”, “wash”, etc. Second, the lyric was analyzed for its porosity. For example, if a lyric had a religious term, but it was said in the context of a secular activity, it was categorized in Category 4: Secular Grounding. Furthermore, this study utilized a frequency metric to determine which categories were displayed the most throughout the album. These frequencies were then turned into percentages by taking the frequency of each category

and dividing it by the total number of lyrics analyzed (101). For example, Category 1: Liminality had a frequency of 26, so it had a percentage of 25.74%. This means that Category 1 took up 25.74% of the total amount of lyrics that were studied. This information will be used to prove which category is the most prevalent throughout the entire album. Other information that will be studied are the thematic cluster categories that were revealed in research. This is essentially a way to see how each category progressed throughout the album. For example, in the first song, Wake Me Up the percentage of Category 1 was 37.5, but then in song 2 Cry for Me we can see it decrease to 14.28%. This information will be used to prove if certain songs were category-specific and the overall progression of a category throughout the entire album. This will help showcase how The Weeknd constructs his religious identity throughout the album, not just in its entirety. This thematic cluster tracking also allows us to see thematic clusters, which can be used to prove aspects of the narrative. For example, if a song has a high percentage of Category 2 but also a high percentage of Category 4, it might suggest an internal conflict between old habits and new goals. This further prevents the album from being analyzed from a flat perspective, where moods and themes are just being guessed, and allows it to be based on numerical data.

V. Results

The results of this study are based on the qualitative thematic content analysis of 101 distinct lyrics from 20 out of the 22 tracks on The Weeknd's *Hurry Up Tomorrow* album that were categorized into four thematic areas: Liminality (25.74%), Atonement (32.67%), Transcendence (18.88%), and Secular Grounding (22.77%). These findings suggest that while the album serves

as the “Paradiso” or resolution phase of the trilogy, the construction of The Weeknd’s religious identity is more defined by the process of seeking forgiveness (Category 2) and navigating the transition between states (Category 1).

Category	Frequency	Percentage
1: Liminality	26	25.74%
2: Atonement	33	32.67%
3: Transcendence	19	18.88%
4: Secular Grounding	23	22.77%
Total	101	100%

Table 1 (made by researcher)

As further shown in table one, Atonement was the most prevalent theme as it accounted for nearly a third of the data. This indicates that the main method of constructing spiritual identity is through the lens of penthos, or inner sorrow, as described by Campesato (2023). Lyrical examples of this are “I hope my confession is enough”, “Wash me with your fire”, and “Set my heart on fire”, which all demonstrate a direct shift from the first album in the trilogy, *After Hours*, as that album revolved around sin and pain. Category 1 (Liminality) and Category 4 (Secular Grounding) also maintain a significant presence in the album. The frequency of liminal language suggests that the persona’s or narratives’ construction of spiritual identity is not instant but rather still somewhat caught in the purgatory of the previous album, *Dawn FM*. Category 3 (Transcendence), while representing the goal of the “Man in a Hole” arc (Neto et al., 2025), it

also has the lowest frequency at 18.88%. This suggests that the spiritual identity in *Hurry Up Tomorrow* is not fully settled, but rather a constant striving towards peace. This is shown by the lyric “fighting for the light” in Track 15 Give Me Mercy.

Thematic Clusters:

Act I:

The opening songs of the album (Tracks 1-7) are characterized by Category 1 (Liminality) and Category 4 (Secular Grounding). This is backed by the frequencies of the categories as Category 4 (Secular Grounding) was seen 12 times and Category 1 (Liminality) was seen 10. We see in the songs “Wake Me Up” and “Cry for Me”, that the persona is paralyzed, using lyrics such as “fades to black” and “penthouse prison”. In this section the spiritual identity is being blocked by fame and all the aspects of a celebrity's lifestyle. The lyrics “Cleanse me with your fire” has direct association with the bottom of the hole described by Neto et al (2025), where the persona is aware of their sin but spiritually stuck by said sin. Another highly important lyric we see in “Cry for Me” is “wash my fears with whisky tears”, this is a perfect example of the porosity described by Foley (2020), where the persona uses the word wash with the secular word whisky. In “Reflections Laughing”, we see lots of references to his career's success and multiple instances of how they are bittersweet. For example, the lyric “crown” which refers to his fame and being one of the top charting artists, and the lyric “golden blade” which in context of the lyrics refers to a religious figure (Category 2 atonement) but taken independently can refer to the pain of fame and it ultimately causing him to bleed. The first part of this album concludes with the realization from the persona that material wealth is only resulting in more negative effects,

further backed by the lyric in “Open Heart” “All the silver and cold only made my skin cold” directly showcasing the bad effects of his success. This sets the stage for a religious intervention or search for divine assistance.

Act II:

In the middle part of this album (Tracks 8-15), we can see the most identity reconstruction, as it is marked by an increase in Category 2 (Atonement) appearances. This is backed by the frequencies of the categories appearing with the most being Category 2 (Atonement), (13 times). This act shifts from the starting tracks themes of being a victim to fame and such, and rather is more centered around taking responsibility for his moral failures, asking for forgiveness, and changing his lifestyle. Starting with the song “Enjoy the Show”, where he states that “I’m not violent to my body anymore” indicating a stage of healing and moving away from the self destructive tendencies of his persona. We can see in “Niagara falls”, the construction of a religious identity is backed by the lyric "swallowed my pride" where the persona gives up his ego. Another lyric from this song is “set my heart on fire” which is a reoccurring theme of utilizing fire in order to cleanse one's sins. This lyric showcases how the persona is transforming. A peak in this phase of atonement occurs in “Give me Mercy”. The language in this becomes explicitly directed towards mercy, as the song entails. Lyrics such as “Give me mercy”, “forgive me”, and “give it all away to feel your grace” exhibit a desire to be cleansed, freed, and forgiven for his sins and to start a new path to the light

Act III:

This final part of the album (Tracks 16-20) is complex in the sense that it is based around

Category 3 (Transcendence) but the lyrics themselves were coded more frequently for Category 1 (Liminality) and Category 2 (Atonement) more often (both appearing 8 times while Category 3 Transcendence appears 6). For example in the final and title track "Hurry up Tomorrow", the persona express a desire for "Heaven", but the lyric "drownin in the same tub" and the plea "Wash me with your fire" shows that he is still exhibiting aspects of Category 2 (Atonement) and Category 1 (Liminality) (wanting to be cleansed from sin and being paralyzed in the tub). This suggests that The Weeknd's religious identity is not a full ascension but rather a constant striving to peace rather than falling into "The Abyss". We know that the persona chooses Tomorrow over the abyss but we don't exactly know if he reaches it yet. The line "Hurry up Tomorrow" itself showcases that Tomorrow, heaven, peace, etc isn't here despite the persona asking it to "hurry up". This shows that despite the non-arrival of "tomorrow" the persona would still rather chase it than not.

Thematic Clusters

Table 2 (made by researcher)

VI. Discussion/Conclusion

The data and results reveal that The Weeknd's spiritual identity in *Hurry Up Tomorrow* is not a static state of enlightenment but rather a dynamic fluid and ongoing process of transformation.

While the album is positioned as the resolution or “Paradiso” of the trilogy, the quantitative analysis contradicts the assumption of a complete and full ascension. Instead, the highest frequency of Category 2 (Atonement) (32.67%) directly suggests that The Weeknd's spiritual identity is constructed through the act of confession rather than the act of transcendence. This finding challenges the “Man in a Hole” narrative arc described by Neto et al. (2025). While the trilogy follows the structural climb toward redemption, the lyrical content suggests the persona is

still tied to secular activities as Category 4 (Secular Grounding) (22.77%). This supports Foley's (2020) framework of porosity, as the boundaries between sacred and secular remain fluid throughout the album. The Weeknd does not abandon his secular self to become spiritual but rather utilizes musical elements and the deep theological message to make his moral failure easier to accept. Ultimately, the spiritual identity constructed throughout the album is one of yearning. By concluding the trilogy with a title track that pleads “Hurry Up Tomorrow”, Tesfaye showcases that heaven or Tomorrow is a place not reached or arrived yet. The significance of this research lies in its demonstration that contemporary R&B can function as a sacred expression of self, where the artist's persona is resurrected through the public admission of sin. The Weeknd demonstrates that a spiritual identity is not the absence of sin but the pursuit of Tomorrow.

VII. Limitations

While this study allows for a systematic look at the construction of a religious identity in *Hurry Up Tomorrow*, several limitations must be acknowledged. First is the subjectivity of qualitative coding, which is an inherent challenge. Although the codebook is grounded in the respected theological frameworks of Foley (2020) and Zangwill (2024), the interpretation of liminality or atonement in R&B lyrics can be fluid. For example, a reference to “light” might be coded as Category 3 (Transcendence), but to a different researcher it might be interpreted as a secular reference to fame, despite the presence of Category 4. Secondly, this study excludes non-lyrical data. Noted in the literature review, soundscapes and visual semiotics (Preniqi et al 2023) and (Yudhanto & Risdianto, 2022), are essential to understanding The Weeknd's world-building and narrative creation. By focusing strictly on the texts from Genius.com, the research may miss the

spiritual weight conveyed through key shifts or any other nontextual evidence that could signify redemption. The new understanding established by this study is that spiritual identity in contemporary R&B is not defined by the attainment of a pure state but by the public confession of sin.

VIII. Future Implications

The findings of this study carry significant implications for the field of musicology and the study of contemporary religion, and they extend far beyond the discography of The Weeknd. This research offers a critical perspective into the relationship between culture and modern spirituality. First, this study suggests that there is a need to shift a common method used by theologians and musicologists to categorize religious music. The porosity identified in this research suggests that R&B and Hip-Hop albums may now function as primary sites for spiritual formation and moral reflection. Future research should explore how listeners take in these narratives to navigate their own moral failures. Secondly, this research provides a template for analyzing the “Man in a Hole” arc in multi-album narratives. While previous studies have focused on the structural presence of an arc, this study proves that the content in the “climbing” phase is more complex than a simple ascent. Scholars can apply this thematic content analysis to other narrative and world building artists to determine if modern artists need to confess in order to define their music and self.

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